

Elderly Abuse in India: Understanding the Contributing Factors and Preventive Strategies

Kanu Priya¹

ABSTRACT

Old age is often crowned with an inevitable series of biological, psychological, and social changes that occur over time. This also involves changes in the roles, responsibilities, and social relations, along with other social determinants including financial management, property matters, healthcare, safety, etc. While few households cherish old age within the family, a considerable number of family members disregard the elderly by way of ignorance, neglect, and abuse. Changing family structures, lifestyle modification, and shifting demographics are a few factors that have triggered the situation worldwide.

To avert this hidden pandemic, the Government and Non-Government agencies in India are working diligently on public awareness to protect and support the vulnerable elders. Regardless, society is still struggling to understand the consequences of elder abuse including but not limited to legal, social, financial, and professional impact on the perpetrators. This paper delves into the complexities of elder abuse in the Indian context. It is aimed to examine the contributing factors at individual, family, and societal levels and preventive strategies to address this issue.

Keywords: Elder Abuse, Elder Exploitation, Violence

INTRODUCTION:

Parents were revered and treated with a great deal of respect in ancient India. The family structure was typically patriarchal, and the roles of parents, were crucial to the social and moral training of children (Gogineni, R.R., et al., 2018.). It was instilled in children to respect and obey their parents. An ancient Indian literature called the Taittiriya Upanishad highlights the tremendous respect that children were required to exhibit for their parents by emphasizing the significance of considering them as deities. In a same vein, sons and daughters had obligations to their parents. They were supposed to

take care of them and see to their well-being, particularly as they grew older. This was considered a religious and moral obligation (Baghel, R., 2023). Children were socialized to accept the authority of those above them in the hierarchy (Adler, P.A. & Adler, P., 1996).

Mothers were particularly revered. The societal norms placed a high value on motherhood, often glorifying it. However, in many rituals and societal functions, the role of women, including mothers, was often overshadowed by men (Bhattacharji, 1990). Parenting in ancient India combined authority with guidance.

¹ Social Work Practitioner, Chandigarh

Parents were responsible for instilling moral values, life skills, and cultural norms in their children (Shahbaz, 2024). In the later stages of life, parents often moved out of the family as part of the ashram system, which was a traditional stage of life where they would renounce worldly duties and focus on spiritual growth (Joseph, 2023). Although, the ideals of respect and loyalty to one's parents are told to be deeply rooted in India culture, this respect may not always translate into everyday actions (Satpathy, B.B., 2015). A study by Helpage India reveals a concerning reality that more than half (58.4%) of senior adults in the nation face elder abuse in some form. The elderly in Delhi (73.5%) and Chandigarh (83.5%) had the strongest opinions on this (Source: TOI; Helpage India report 2022). According to the World Health Organization (2002), "a single or repeated act, or lack of appropriate action, occurring within any relationship where there is an expectation of trust, which causes harm or distress to an older person" (Maurya, P. et al., 2022). In simpler terms, elder abuse is the deliberate act, or inaction, by a caregiver or someone in a trusted relationship that causes harm to an adult aged 60 or older. The same report also reveals that around 1 in 6 adults aged 60 and above reported experiencing abuse in a community setting within the past year (Source: WHO). Financial exploitation, abandonment, neglect (Kurrle SE., 2004), and a serious loss of dignity and respect are just a few of the ways that this abuse can be exhibited. This involves various forms of abuse including but not limited to physical, sexual, psychological, neglect and financial abuse that are considered violation of human rights there are other elderly issues

like intentional torts, malpractice etc. A research study by Helpage India have shown that elderly people frequently experience financial exploitation (24.2%), verbal abuse (38.3%), neglect (32.8%), and disrespect (57%) (Source: Helpage India report 2022).

According to the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, the country's elderly population has been on a continuous rise since 1961, largely attributed to decreasing mortality rates. Between 2001 and 2011, the senior demographic expanded by approximately 27 million people. Similarly, a Report on Population Projections for India and States 2011-2036 projects that in 2021, India would have approximately 138 million senior citizens, with women accounting for 71 million and men for 67 million (Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation).

The number of elder abuse incidents in India is expected to rise due to the country's increasing population ageing. This data originates from a 2022 study by Maurya, P. et al., which suggests elder abuse is more prevalent among females. Across the studied states, females comprised 52.82% of the reported cases, while males accounted for 47.18%. Notably, the majority (59.47%) of abused elders belonged to the 60-69 age group. Furthermore, a report by Helpage India (2023) revealed a strong correlation between the prevalence of elder abuse and women's perception of the issue. In states with higher rates of elder mistreatment against women, over half of older women acknowledged its prevalence in society. Kerala (87%) and Uttarakhand (73%) had the highest agreement among older women, while

Odisha (78%) and Himachal Pradesh (70%) saw a surprisingly high proportion of women denying the problem exists (Source: Helpage India report 2023). As India's population ages, several factors contribute to the increased risk of elder abuse.

ELDERLY DEMOGRAPHICS

Ageing populations are worldwide phenomena. According to World Population Prospects 2022, the percentage of persons 65 and older is growing faster than that of those under 65. It is anticipated that the proportion of people 65 and older worldwide would increase from 10% in 2022 to 16% in 2050 (Source: Ageing the United Nation; World Population Prospects 2022). Three major categories as mentioned by the World Health Organisation (WHO) can be used to understand the age group of older people are **Energetic and fit**: self-sufficient, just retired, seeking chances for gainful involvement (*mostly in the 60-75 year age range*). **Self-sufficient**: financially independent, unable to work, suffering from health problems (*mostly in the 75-*

85 age range). **Dependent**: ill, crippled, or frail (*usually older than 85*) (Source: Changing Needs Of Old People in India 2021; Yojana Magazine 2013).

FACTOR CONTRIBUTING TO ELDER ABUSE

The neglect and abuse of elderly individuals was first documented in 1975 by British scientific publications (Baker 1975, Burston 1977). An abuser is defined as someone who consistently or repeatedly exhibits cruelty or violence toward another person or animal. In figure 1 it is noted that the elder economic dependence ratio is trending upward is one of the factor. The percentage rose to 13.1% in 2001, 14.2% in 2011, 15.7% in 2021, and 20.1% in 2031. Additionally, the dependence ratio is on the rise for both men and women, with projections for 2021 showing that the ratios will be 14.8% and 16.7%, respectively (Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation). The subsequent wave of research has helped to understand the prevalence, causes, and types of elder abuse, as well as shaping policy responses.

Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation

NATURE OF ELDER ABUSE

There are several types of abuse, and it's critical to determine which kind is occurring since each has a particular set of contributing circumstances and solutions. The types are listed below:

1) Physical Abuse: Physical coercion or the imposition of bodily pain or harm is known as physical abuse. Signs include physical constraint, shoving, scorching, slapping, and improper use of drugs (Kurrle SE., 2004). Unfortunately, physical abuse of elderly individuals is a prevalent issue. Here are a couple of recent cases: In October 2023, India Today incident reported that an elderly woman in Punjab's Ropar district was rescued from her home after being allegedly beaten by her son, his wife, and their grandson. A woman in Kerala was arrested in December 2023 after video footage of her physical abuse towards her elderly mother-in-law was shared by News 18.

2) Sexual Abuse: Sexual Abuse includes, uninvited touching, and sexual contact without consent (Post, L. et al., 2010). Unfortunately, this issue continues to be prevalent. Recent news reports highlight a few such cases. A 100-year-old woman has died after being raped by a drunk man in northern India, according to a report by SBS Australia.

3) Psychological abuse: included verbal aggression, threatening behavior, humiliating or taunting behaviors often more prevalent than physical abuse. One of case mention below:

4) Financial abuse: Financial abuse was described as financial exploitation, which includes misusing someone else's money, assets, or property (Post, L. et al., 2010) Highlighting an example from this issue by showcasing a real-life case

5) Neglect: It is explored through research of Kurrle SE on elder abuse. When an older person is neglected, it means that a carer and family member have neglected to provide them with basic requirements such as enough food, clothes, housing, medical attention, or dental treatment (Kurrle SE., 2004).

IDENTIFYING THE HIDDEN CRUELTY TO ELDER

Unfortunately, elder abuse often remains hidden due to several factors (Choi, N. G., & Mayer, J. 2000):

1) Elder abuse is mostly a covert issue that is typically carried out by family members quietly in the house (Jagmohan S. Jandu et al., 2024).

2) The alleged victim's illness, cognitive deficits, and ensuring lack of cooperation may make it difficult to identify and prove assault.

3) Psychological, sexual, financial, emotional, and Physical abuse and caregiver negligence, are all included in the broad category of maltreatment known as elder abuse and neglect (Wolf, R. S. & Pillemer, K., 1994).

4) Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's disease, and dementia, disability, etc. are few examples of severe physical conditions and are considered risk factors for abuse that is likely to occur in a small percentage of these patients (Coyne A, et al., 1993).

5) Elder abuse victims and offenders sometimes conceal harmful acts from investigators because they feel embarrassed of them (Quinn, M. J. & Tomita, S. K. 1995). The dependence and vulnerability caused by declining health can make elders susceptible to various forms of abuse, including physical, financial, and emotional abuse.

Source-National Institute of Social Defence

ARE OLD AGE HOMES THE NEW SAFEST PLACE FOR ELDERLY POPULATION?

“The elderly, whose roots young people need in order to grow into adulthood”- Pope Francis

However, this idea is challenged by the growing trend of nuclear families in India. This shift leaves many elderly individuals lacking adequate family care. Studies have shown HelpAge India (2022) instances of aggression, improper behavior, and rejection of older adults by their families. Various factors, including financial strain, generational differences, or limited living space may drive these actions (Source: Importance of old age homes).

In response to this growing need, the Indian government, under the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment (2021), provides shelter for elders through 551 facilities, serving the total beneficiaries of 16290 (Source: Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment). There are various forms

of elder abuse that necessitate a multi-pronged approach that combines legal protection, public awareness campaigns, and accessible support systems.

EXISTING POLICY AND STRATEGIES FOR ELDER ABUSE IN INDIA

The ministries and department of Indian government are providing care and welfare to elders. These consist of things like food, housing, financial stability, social security, medical attention, and awareness. Programs and schemes exist to directly support older adults, including: providing mobile medical care, doorstep banking, old age homes, etc (Source: National policy on senior citizens).

They will also be protected from exploitation and abuse and will have an equal part in development. The government creates laws and policies for older people like National Policy on Older Persons, Code of Criminal Procedure, Maintenance Act, Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007, etc. (Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation). Seniors who meet a specified yearly income threshold are entitled for free legal assistance. Anyone over 60 is eligible to apply for free legal services or help. The Income Ceiling Limit that is specified in Section 12(h) of the Act to get free legal services in various States for Delhi, Chandigarh, Haryana, and Punjab is 3 Lakh (Source: National Legal Services Authority).

Under the legislative framework, both Hindu adoption and Maintenance act 1956 and Muslim Personal Law mention that the children are bound to entitled for the maintenance of parents whereas in

Muslims they also have to take care of paternal and maternal grandparents if they are poor. In Section 125 to 128, Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 allow a parent who is unable to support oneself to get maintenance from a major child. This is secular legislation, which applies to all faiths. The court may even impose a fine for their violation of the order if they do not pay the maintenance amount.

The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizen Act, 2007 This Act provides:

a) Maintenance of parents or senior citizens by children or relatives should be mandatory and subject to tribunal proceedings;

b) Senior persons may revoke the transfer of their property in the event that their relatives ignore/neglect them; and

c) Senior citizens shall have access to adequate medical care and security. According to this statute, leaving a senior citizen by someone who is responsible for or protecting them is a crime that has a maximum sentence of three months in prison, a fine of up to Rs. 5,000, or both. These policies translate into concrete benefits through schemes like the Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme and Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana, offering financial assistance and healthcare access. However, addressing social isolation and providing adequate caregiving options require further initiatives alongside these existing programs.

CONCLUSION

India's rapidly growing elderly population faces a unique set of challenges. While aging can be a time of beauty surrounded by loved ones, the reality for many seniors

is marred by societal biases, inadequate legal protections, and a lack of social awareness. These factors can create fear, vulnerability, and isolation.

The care of the elderly in India in contrast to the West. The Western countries generally have more social assistance and healthcare systems to support their elderly populations. Governments often provide comprehensive pension plans, and long-term care facilities. Additionally, there are strong legal protections in place to prevent elder abuse and neglect. While India has made strides in recent years, its social welfare infrastructure is still developing. The National Old Age Pension Plan is one of the several initiatives the government has created to assist the elderly, but access, cost, high-quality care, and a robust legal system continue to be the key issues.

To address these pressing concerns, a multifaceted approach. First, strengthening legal frameworks to safeguard the rights of older adults is crucial. Second, raising public awareness about elder abuse is essential to empower both victims and potential perpetrators. By educating elders about their rights and the resources at their disposal, we can empower them to advocate for themselves and seek support. Additionally, spreading awareness among the general public of the value of honoring and taking care of senior citizens may contribute to the development of a more compassionate and inclusive community. Third, Providing access to quality healthcare, social services, and support networks is essential for elders. This includes expanding home-based care options, providing affordable housing, and promoting intergenerational programs.

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